

TEMPERING IS THE BASIS OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE FOR PRESCHOOLERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11018685>

Abstract

the article discusses the tempering of a child, as well as solving the problems of a healthy lifestyle for preschoolers

Key words

Physical perfection, sport, physical qualities, individual, tempering, process, regime, function, healthy lifestyle

Hardening is the training of the body's defenses under the influence of irritating environmental factors; it is a set of measures aimed at increasing resistance to cold, heat, solar radiation, drafts. This is an improvement in the operation of the thermoregulation system. The child should perceive all procedures with a good mood, for this it is necessary to observe the most comfortable conditions: the appropriate temperature in the room, a warm dry bed, the opportunity to dry off after water treatments, change wet clothes. The procedures should be of a playful nature.

Lifestyle is a daily, habitual activity in the conditions of the existence of the environment, aimed at ensuring the functional provision of the body and the regular performance of current life processes. The lifestyle is regulated by the rhythm, intensity and habitual ways of acting in the environment of the organism's existence. To change the lifestyle, it is necessary to change the current parameters that regulate the course of this process (all or partially), depending on to what extent (in which direction) it is necessary to change the state of the body. For the further development of the system of concepts of modern health pedagogy, the integrating, synthesizing function of the concept of "healthy lifestyle" is extremely important. The concept of "healthy lifestyle" reflects the unity of psychological, social, pedagogical and biomedical studies of people's lifestyle. Consequently, this concept, reflecting the main ways of organizing people's life activities from the point of view of their health and diseases, allows us to bring into a single theoretical scheme the structural, substantive and dynamic features of these processes within the framework of research on people's lifestyle.

This is a complex of wellness activities that ensure the harmonious development and strengthening of health, improving people's performance, and prolonging their creative longevity. The main elements of a healthy lifestyle are fruitful work, optimal motor regime, personal hygiene, rational nutrition, rejection of bad habits and, of course, hardening. There is still no unambiguous definition of the concept of "hardening", although it has been known for a long time. The concept has evolved over time. That's what V. wrote about hardening. Dahl: "... to accustom to all hardships, needs, bad weather, to educate in severity." As can be seen, hardening implies an increase in resistance not only to heat or cold, but also to a number of other adverse effects. Subsequently, the definition of the concept of "hardening" clearly showed a tendency to narrow it, this can be traced in the definition: "Hardening of the body is a system of procedures that enhance the body's resistance to adverse environmental influences, the development of conditioned reflex reactions of thermoregulation in order to improve it. During hardening, the body develops resistance to cooling and thus to so-called colds and some other diseases."

In this definition, the hardening effect is reduced to increasing the body's resistance to cold. But the content of tempering is not sufficiently disclosed here. According to modern ideas, hardening is the adaptation of the body to the effects of adverse environmental factors, or, as N. A. Semashko said, the training of the body's defenses. The essence of hardening is to improve the mechanisms of formation, preservation and return of heat, the systematic effect of air, water and sunlight on the human body contribute to the formation of conditioned reflexes that adapt the body to temperature fluctuations in the environment. The effect of hardening is not only that the body's resistance to diseases increases, primarily colds, but also that during hardening the human nervous system strengthens, metabolism in the body increases, the activity of the heart, lungs, other organs and systems improves. And as a result of all this, the overall endurance and performance of a person increases. Hardening by air, water and the sun is the most widespread.

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Hardening of the body is an effective means of improving health, reducing morbidity and increasing the level of working capacity of children. Hardening is not only wiping or dousing, but also everyday routine procedures that do not require special organization, additional time: being indoors and outdoors in appropriate clothes, washing with cool water, sleeping with an open window, window, active physical education on the playground.

The sun, air and water are factors that, when systematically exposed, increase the body's resistance to changing weather conditions.

Air acts as a complex irritant, enhancing metabolic processes, increasing the amount of hemoglobin and red blood cells, strengthening the nervous system. Its beneficial effect is also manifested in the child's mood - he becomes cheerful and cheerful. It is necessary to use fresh air for hardening purposes constantly, at

any time of the year. The cold winter air in combination with active physical exercises and games is especially beneficial. For the proper development of a child, it is important that he be outdoors for 4-5 hours in winter, and almost all day in summer. By organizing outdoor walks for children, adults should create conditions for their active activity.

A good way to promote health is hardening with water. Children love to play with her, such activities improve their mood, cause him joyful emotions. This should be used to improve the health of the body. It is better to start water treatments in the warmer months. Wash the children with cool water. First, wash your hands up to the elbows, then your neck, face.

One of the effective ways of hardening is contrast dousing of the legs: first with cold water -24,-25 degrees, then warm 36 degrees and cold again.

The most powerful hardening agent is bathing in a pond. For a healthy child, it is acceptable at the age of 2 years at an air temperature of 25 -28 degrees and water at least 22 degrees.

It must be remembered that the hardening effect of the applied influences depends on the systematicity, continuity of use, gradually increasing intensity of procedures, taking into account the individual sensitivity of the child.

The basic rules of hardening are as follows:

1. Hardening procedures should be carried out only if the child is healthy. You can start at any season of the year, but it's better in summer.

2. Continuity. If the cold factor affects the body systematically, repeatedly, a rapid reaction of blood vessels to the influence of low air and water temperatures occurs. On the contrary, the randomness of tempering procedures, long breaks reduce the body's resistance, and can lead to the opposite effect.

3. Gradualness. It is unacceptable, having decided to temper a child, immediately pour cool water on him, send him for walks in inclement weather lightly dressed. This will certainly lead to the fact that the baby will catch a cold, and the mother will henceforth be afraid of hardening, like "fire". You need to start carefully, moving on to stronger hardening procedures gradually.

4. It is necessary to take into account the individual characteristics of the child. For example, excitable, "nervous" children sometimes react badly to cold water.

5. Constantly monitor the child's reaction to hardening procedures. If the baby shivers during pouring or taking an air bath, his skin becomes "goose bumps", it means that he has not yet adapted to this temperature. The next time

the procedure should be carried out, starting with the dosage that did not cause any negative effects.

6. It is necessary to strive to ensure that hardening is liked by children, perceived by them as fun.

7. If the temperature rises, runny nose, cough, loose stools - it is necessary to suspend hardening or carry out at a gentle level. Hypotrophy, anemia, rickets are not contraindications to hardening.

8. When starting tempering, create healthy living conditions for the child, a normal psychological atmosphere in the family, and sufficient sleep. It is necessary to ventilate the room at least 4-5 times a day, at least 10-15 minutes each time.

9. Children 1.5 years and older need to walk at least twice a day for 2.5-3.0 hours. In winter, at lower temperatures, walking time is limited. Children from the age of 2.5-3 years can be taught to ski, skate, scooter, bike. In the summer, there is no need to prohibit playing in the water, walking barefoot on the ground, on the grass, on the sand by the river. Clothes are of great importance: it is important that they are the right size, the child does not freeze and does not overheat in them. All these measures also have a certain hardening effect.

Special tempering activities are: gymnastics, massage, air, light-air, water treatments, including swimming, reflexology, sauna.

In different age periods, hardening is carried out in different ways, according to the principle from simple to complex.

Hardening methods:

1. Air baths: in winter in the room, in summer outside at a temperature of +22 + 28 C, preferably in the morning. You can start at the age of two months, for the first time for 1 minute 2-3 times a day, after 5 days increase the time by 1 minute, bringing it to 15 minutes by 6 months and to + 16 Seconds by the year.

2. Hardening by sunlight: it is better in the shade of trees, in calm weather, at an air temperature of at least + 22 C. Starting from the age of 1.5-2 years, children can sunbathe in only panties, the duration from 3 to 10 minutes, increasing in 7-10 days to 20-25 minutes. The optimal time is from 9 a.m. to 12 p.m.

It is unacceptable for children to stay "in the sun" at an air temperature of +30 C and above, due to possible overheating.

3. Wet wiping: performed with a piece of clean flannel soaked in water and wrung out, once a day for 1-2 minutes. Start with the hands - from the fingers to the shoulder, then the legs, chest, stomach and back until a slight redness. The

water temperature at the age of 3-4 years is + 32 C, 5-6 years + 30 C, 6-7 years + 28 C; after 3-4 days, it is reduced by 1 C and brought to + 22 + 18 C in summer and +25 + 22 C in winter. At the end, the child should be warmly dressed. In case of a break, start with dry wipes.

4. Hardening of the oropharynx: rinsing the oropharynx with any disinfectant herb 3-4 times a day (preferably after visiting kindergarten, school, cinema, etc.). After cooking, divide the infusion in half, rinse alternately, once a week, reduce the temperature in the second glass by 0.5-1 C. Start at a temperature of + 24 + 25 C.

5. Foot baths: dousing the feet for 20-30 seconds with water at a temperature of +32 + 34 C, with a gradual decrease once a week by 1 C to + 10 C. You can alternate cold and warm pouring, 3-6 times. At the end, the legs are rubbed to the pink color of the skin.

6. General dousing: start from 9-10 months, do not drench your head, while the child is standing or sitting. The water temperature under the age of one year is +36 C, 1-3 years +34 C, older than 3 years +33 C. Gradually decreasing by 1 C per week, to +28 C in winter and +22 C in summer. Duration is up to 1.5 minutes. After that, rub the body with a towel until it turns pink.

7. Shower: after 1.5 years. It is better in the morning for 30-90 seconds at a water temperature of + 34 C, gradually reducing to + 28 C in winter and +22 C in summer.

8. Sauna: start with one visit for 5-7 minutes on the bottom step (shelf), it is advisable to put a woolen cap on the child's head. In the future, the number of visits increases up to three times. After each set, you need to cool down for 10 minutes, preferably in the shower. In the bath and after visiting it, it is necessary to take a small amount of berry juice or herbal tea. You can visit the sauna from the age of 2-3. It is contraindicated to visit the bathhouse for children with severe chronic and congenital diseases.

9. Swimming: one of the most effective forms of hardening. It combines the influence of water, air, temperature, and the child's motor activity. You can start training from the first months of life, but under the mandatory guidance of an experienced instructor.

10. Effective hardening measures are physical therapy and massage, which should be carried out by qualified specialists.

Hardening can be carried out for most children, but first you should contact your pediatrician at your place of residence, it is desirable to follow a certain sequence in increasing the hardening loads. Positive results can be achieved

only with the perseverance and patience of demanding moms and dads, who should become an example of a healthy lifestyle for their children.

Hardening is most often considered as the process of adapting the body to changing weather and climate conditions. But, speaking of hardening as a means of physical education, we mean not only the adaptation of the body, which occurs under the influence of adverse conditions. Hardening should be considered as a conscious application in a certain system of measures that increase the body's resistance, nurturing the ability to apply quickly and without harm to health to various environmental conditions. Hardening should begin from early childhood and continue throughout life, modifying the forms and methods of its application depending on age.

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